

Parallel Genetic Algorithms Clustering for Handling Recruitment Problem

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Abstract : This research presents a study to handle the recruitment services system. It aims to enhance a business intelligence system by embedding data mining in its core engine and to facilitate the link between job searchers and recruiters companies. The purpose of this study is to present an intelligent management system for supporting recruitment services based on data mining methods. It consists to apply segmentation on the extracted job postings offered by the different recruiters. The details of the job postings are associated to a set of relevant features that are extracted from the web and which are based on critical criterion in order to define consistent clusters. Thereafter, we assign the job searchers to the best cluster while providing a ranking according to the job postings of the selected cluster. The performance of the proposed model used is analyzed, based on a real case study, with the clustered job postings dataset and classified job searchers dataset by using some metrics.

Keywords : job postings, job searchers, clustering, genetic algorithms, business intelligence

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